

DIGITAL TOOLS IN SCHOOL ASTRONOMY: VISUAL LEARNING OF LUNAR PHASES AND ECLIPSES USING STELLARIUM

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Abstract. *This article examines the use of digital technologies in astronomy education, with a particular focus on the Stellarium software for studying the phases of the Moon and eclipses. Astronomy, as one of the most dynamically developing scientific disciplines, requires modern pedagogical approaches that can effectively engage students and foster the development of their scientific thinking. The paper proposes a lesson plan that includes a theoretical component, a demonstration using the Stellarium program, and practical tasks aimed at modeling astronomical phenomena. As a result of employing digital tools, students gain access to observations that were previously unavailable and develop analytical and critical thinking skills. The study demonstrates how digital technologies can enrich the educational process, making it more interactive and engaging while preserving its scientific rigor.*

Keywords: *astronomy, digital technologies, Stellarium software, lunar phases, eclipses, interactive learning, scientific thinking, modeling of astronomical phenomena.*

INTRODUCTION

Astronomy, as one of the oldest and at the same time one of the most dynamically developing fields of natural science, occupies an important place in school education. The study of celestial bodies and cosmic phenomena not only broadens students' understanding of the surrounding world but also develops essential skills of scientific thinking, observation, and analytical reasoning [Kondakova, E. V. *Why It Is Important to Study Astronomy at School*. Regional Education: Current Trends, 2017, No. 1, pp. 71–76; Vinnik, M. A. *On the Role of Astronomical Education in Teaching and Development of Students*. Bulletin of the Moscow State Regional University. Series: Pedagogy, 2010, No. 2, pp. 169–173]. Modern technologies and digital tools significantly enrich the educational process, making it more interactive and visually demonstrative. The integration of digital technologies into the educational process, particularly in astronomy, enables teachers to create a multi-level learning environment that stimulates students' cognitive activity and facilitates deeper engagement with the subject matter [Bezrukov, P. O. *Opportunities for the Use of Digital Technologies in Astronomy Lessons in Upper Secondary School to Achieve Educational Outcomes*. Teaching Physics and Astronomy in General and Vocational Education, 2019, pp. 26–27; Shefer, O. R., Lebedeva, T. N., Nosova, L. S. *Internet Resources in Teaching Astronomy at School*. Lomonosov Readings in Altai: Fundamental Problems of Science and Education, 2017, pp. 850–853; Khabarov, A. *The Use of Internet Technologies in Astronomy Lessons*. Computer Tools in Education, 2006, No. 2, pp. 3–8].

Historically, astronomy has relied on direct observations of the night sky conducted using telescopes and other analog instruments. However, modern digital technologies such as virtual planetariums, simulations of cosmic phenomena, and specialized astronomical software, including Stellarium have provided access to data and models that were previously unavailable at the level

of school education. These resources enable students not only to visualize complex astronomical processes but also to actively participate in research-oriented activities, analyze real data, and draw conclusions based on observations.

Nevertheless, the effective integration of digital technologies into the educational process requires carefully structured lesson planning. It is essential for teachers to take into account both methodological considerations and the age-specific characteristics of students, as well as the technological capabilities of the educational institution. The use of digital tools should not be an end in itself, but rather a means of enhancing knowledge acquisition and fostering a sustained interest in astronomy among learners. In this context, the development of lesson plans incorporating digital technologies becomes an important pedagogical objective.

Designing astronomy lessons with the integration of digital technologies involves consideration of multiple factors. Teachers are required not only to adapt lesson content to the use of new tools but also to establish a methodological framework that ensures the most effective assimilation of the material by students.

In this study, we examine the significance of using digital technologies in teaching astronomy, specifically through the example of the lesson “Phases of the Moon and Eclipses.”

LITERATURE REVIEW

Modern digital technologies provide a wide range of tools for teaching astronomy, from simulation software to online observatories and databases of astronomical observations. Programs such as Stellarium, Celestia, and WorldWide Telescope enable the visual demonstration of the motion of celestial bodies, the phases of the Moon, solar and lunar eclipses, as well as other significant astronomical phenomena [Vyborova, N. N. *The Use of the Stellarium Program in the Study of Astronomy at School and University*. Bulletin of Shadrinsk State Pedagogical University, 2019, No. 3 (43), pp. 94–99; Pavlivsky, Yu. G. *A System of Multi-Level Astronomy Tasks as a Means of Forming Subject Competencies of Students through the Use of Information and Communication Technologies*. Shamov Pedagogical Readings of the Scientific School of Educational Systems Management, 2021, pp. 201–203]. These programs have become an essential component of the educational process, providing students with the opportunity to study outer space in an interactive format.

When designing lesson plans that incorporate digital technologies, it is important to consider their integration with traditional teaching methods. Interactive resources should not serve as an end in themselves but rather as a means of facilitating a deeper and more visual understanding of the subject. The structure of the lesson should include both demonstrative elements and practical tasks carried out using digital tools.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive and practice-oriented methodological approach aimed at examining the pedagogical potential of digital tools in school astronomy education. The research focused on the use of Stellarium as an interactive visual learning tool for teaching the topic “Phases of the Moon and Eclipses.” The methodological design was based on lesson modeling, classroom demonstration, student-centered practical tasks, and guided discussion. The lesson structure included four main stages: an introductory theoretical explanation, a digital demonstration of lunar phases, practical modeling of solar and lunar eclipses, and discussion of students’ results.

The main instructional tool used in the study was Stellarium, a virtual planetarium program that enables users to simulate the night sky, observe celestial motion, and model astronomical phenomena in real time. During the lesson, students observed the changing phases of the Moon,

identified the relative positions of the Earth, Moon, and Sun, and modeled the conditions under which solar and lunar eclipses occur. The effectiveness of the lesson was assessed through students' participation, answers to guiding questions, practical reports, and their ability to explain the modeled astronomical phenomena.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Below, a lesson plan on the topic "Phases of the Moon and Eclipses" is presented.

Lesson Topic: Phases of the Moon and Eclipses

1. Introductory Part (10 minutes)

Lesson objectives:

To familiarize students with the phases of the Moon and the mechanism of their formation.

To explain the causes of solar and lunar eclipses.

To develop an understanding of the Moon's motion around the Earth and its influence on observable phenomena.

The teacher begins the lesson by discussing the importance of the Moon for life on Earth.

Several introductory questions may be posed to activate students' prior knowledge:

"How often do you observe the Moon in the sky?"

"Have you noticed that its shape changes?"

"Can anyone explain why the Moon does not always appear the same?"

Following this, the teacher briefly explains that the Moon plays a significant role in Earth's systems it causes tides, influences the climate, and determines the duration of months and calendar cycles in certain cultures.

Introduction to the Topic (7–10 minutes):

The teacher explains that the lesson will address two important astronomical phenomena lunar phases and eclipses. Students are informed that changes in the apparent shape of the Moon are referred to as phases and are related to the relative positions of the Moon, the Earth, and the Sun. For clearer understanding, several key concepts are introduced: new moon, full moon, first quarter, and last quarter.

The teacher then proceeds to the topic of eclipses, explaining that there are two types solar and lunar eclipses. It is briefly clarified that these occur when either the Moon or the Earth blocks the light from the Sun, resulting in these remarkable natural phenomena.

2. Demonstration (15 minutes)

Simulation of Lunar phases using Stellarium

Objectives of the demonstration:

To demonstrate to students how the phases of the Moon change in real time.

To explain the relationship between the Moon's position in its orbit and the phases observed from Earth.

To illustrate the effect of solar illumination of the Moon on the phases visible from Earth.

Preparation for the Demonstration:

Prior to the demonstration, the teacher should launch the Stellarium software on a screen connected to a projector or an interactive whiteboard. The program should be configured to the current date, time, and geographical location. The teacher may заранее (in advance) set the view to the Moon and enable the display of the orbits of the Earth and the Moon, as well as the position of the Sun.

Step 1. Overview of the Stellarium Interface (2 minutes)

The teacher briefly familiarizes students with the main functions of the Stellarium software.

Step 2. Demonstration of the Moon's Orbital Motion (4 minutes)

The teacher begins the demonstration using the current date, displaying the Moon within the program. The following question is posed: "Which phase of the Moon do we currently observe?" Students discuss their responses, and the teacher confirms the correct answer by using Stellarium to zoom in on the Moon and present its current appearance in detail.

The teacher then activates the time-acceleration function in Stellarium, enabling students to observe the Moon's motion along its orbit around the Earth. It is explained that a complete lunar cycle (synodic month) lasts approximately 29.5 days.

The teacher demonstrates how the Moon gradually increases in illumination (waxing phase), progressing from the new moon to the first quarter and subsequently to the full moon. Particular attention is drawn to the fact that during the full moon phase, the Moon is positioned opposite the Sun relative to the Earth.

After completing the demonstration, the teacher poses questions to assess the extent to which students have understood the material:

"In which phase is the Moon fully illuminated?"

"What is the position of the Moon relative to the Earth and the Sun during the new moon?"

"Why do we observe the Moon in different phases?"

The teacher also invites students to complete a short independent task using the Stellarium software:

Task: Change the date in the Stellarium program to the nearest new moon and full moon. Determine when these phases will occur in your region.

3. Practical Assignment (20 minutes): Modeling Eclipses Using Stellarium

Objectives of the assignment:

To teach students to independently model solar and lunar eclipses using the Stellarium program.

To understand the conditions under which eclipses occur.

To develop skills in using digital tools for astronomical observations.

Step 1. Introduction to the assignment (3 minutes)

The teacher briefly explains that students will work with the Stellarium software in order to model two types of eclipses—solar and lunar. Eclipses occur when the Earth, the Moon, and the Sun are aligned in a straight line. The objective of the task is to determine the conditions under which such alignments occur and to understand why eclipses do not take place every month.

Brief Explanation:

A solar eclipse occurs when the Moon is positioned between the Earth and the Sun, blocking sunlight and casting a shadow on the Earth (during the new moon phase).

A lunar eclipse occurs when the Earth is positioned between the Sun and the Moon, and the Moon passes through the Earth's shadow (during the full moon phase).

Instructions:

Students work either individually or in small groups, modeling both types of eclipses using the Stellarium program. Each student or group is required to prepare a report describing the conditions under which eclipses occur.

Step 2. Modeling a Solar Eclipse (10 minutes)

Launching the Stellarium Program and Selecting the Date:

Open Stellarium and, in the search window, enter "Sun." Ensure that the view is centered on the Sun.

Navigate to the time control panel and begin adjusting the date and time to identify the nearest new moon. During this phase, the Moon should be located between the Sun and the Earth.

Example:

Set the date to the nearest new moon and carefully observe how the Moon approaches the Sun. When the Moon is positioned directly in front of the Sun, the program will simulate a solar eclipse.

Determining the Conditions for a Solar Eclipse:

Pay attention to the lunar phase it must be the new moon.

Use the orbit display function (available in the program menu) to observe that the Moon is aligned with the Earth and the Sun.

Reflect on the following questions: "Which part of the Moon is in shadow?" "Where is the Moon located relative to the Earth?"

Increasing the Time Speed:

To better understand the dynamics of the eclipse, increase the time speed. Observe the motion of the Moon relative to the Sun. At the moment of totality, the Sun will be completely obscured by the Moon, and a full shadow (umbra) will be cast upon the Earth.

Documenting the Results:

After identifying a solar eclipse, record the date, time, and coordinates at which the eclipse occurs.

Determine whether the eclipse is total or partial (depending on whether the Moon completely or partially covers the Sun).

Example of a Report for a Solar Eclipse:

Date: October 10, 2024

Time: 12:15 (localtime)

LunarPhase: NewMoon

TypeofEclipse: Total

Conditions: The Moon completely obscured the Sun, resulting in a total solar eclipse.

4. Discussion of Results (10 minutes)

The teacher, together with the students, discusses the outcomes of the practical activity and clarifies complex aspects. The use of such a lesson structure not only reinforces theoretical knowledge but also makes the learning process more engaging. Through digital tools, students are able not merely to memorize material but to observe real examples of its application.

Objectivesofthediscussion:

To consolidate the results of the practical task by discussing students' conclusions.

To ensure that all students have understood the fundamental principles underlying the occurrence of eclipses.

To analyze possible difficulties and errors encountered during the task.

Step 1. General Overview of Results (3 minutes)

The teacher begins the discussion with a brief overview of the practical work completed. It is recalled that students modeled solar and lunar eclipses using the Stellarium software, identifying the dates and conditions under which these phenomena occur.

Questionsforstudents:

“Were you able to find an example of a solar eclipse? In which lunar phase did it occur?”

“What conditions are necessary for a lunar eclipse to occur?”

“Which lunar phases corresponded to the eclipses you modeled?”

The teacher asks several students to report the dates and times they identified for their eclipses and records selected examples on the board for collective discussion.

Step 2. Discussion of Solar Eclipses (3 minutes)

The teacher proceeds with a discussion of the results related to solar eclipse modeling.

Lunar Phases: The teacher уточняет (clarifies) with students the phase of the Moon during which a solar eclipse was observed. All students should confirm that it occurred during the new moon phase.

Position of the Moon: The teacher explains that, for a solar eclipse to occur, the Moon must be positioned between the Earth and the Sun. However, eclipses do not occur at every new moon because the Moon's orbit is inclined relative to the plane of the ecliptic (the Earth's orbital plane around the Sun).

Observational characteristics: The distinction between total and partial solar eclipses is discussed. The teacher may ask:

“Why do you think some eclipses were total, while others were partial?”

The expected response is that the Moon is not always perfectly aligned along the Earth–Sun line, which results in only partial coverage of the solar disk in some cases.

Step 3. Discussion of Lunar Eclipses (3 minutes)

Moving on to lunar eclipses, the teacher poses questions and summarizes key points:

Students should confirm that a lunar eclipse occurs during the full moon phase, when the Moon is positioned behind the Earth relative to the Sun.

The teacher explains that, for a lunar eclipse to occur, the Earth must be located between the Sun and the Moon. The eclipse takes place when the Moon passes through the Earth's shadow. It is further clarified that, as with solar eclipses, the inclination of the Moon's orbit relative to the Earth's orbit prevents eclipses from occurring at every full moon.

The teacher discusses the difference between total and partial lunar eclipses:

A total eclipse occurs when the Moon passes entirely through the Earth's shadow (umbra).

A partial eclipse occurs when the Moon passes through only a portion of the Earth's shadow.

CONCLUSION

The teacher may ask:

“Which types of eclipses did you observe in Stellarium: total or partial? Why, in your opinion, were some eclipses total while others were partial?”

Conclusion of the Discussion:

Eclipses are relatively rare astronomical phenomena that depend on the precise alignment of the Moon, the Earth, and the Sun.

The practical task enabled students to visually observe how and under what conditions eclipses occur, thereby enhancing their understanding of the underlying mechanisms.

Students are encouraged to use the Stellarium program at home to continue observing the Moon and other celestial bodies.

Conclusion

The use of digital technologies in astronomy lessons provides the following outcomes:

Students gain access to astronomical observations that cannot be conducted in a classroom setting or without specialized equipment.

It fosters an understanding of how dynamic celestial processes are related to the positions of the Earth, the Moon, and the Sun.

It develops critical thinking and information analysis skills, as students independently model processes and draw conclusions based on the obtained results.

A lesson on the topic “Phases of the Moon and Eclipses” implemented with the use of the Stellarium software serves as an example of how digital technologies can transform the educational process. They make astronomical phenomena, which are difficult to observe in real life, accessible to every student. The visualization and modeling of complex processes enable students not only to understand astronomical phenomena but also to develop a broader interest in science as a whole.

The application of digital tools such as Stellarium contributes to the creation of interactive, engaging, and educational lessons that remain memorable for students. This approach transforms astronomy from a purely theoretical discipline into a practical science that can be explored without leaving the classroom.

REFERENCES

1. Kondakova, E. V. (2017). Why it is important to study astronomy at school. *Regional Education: Current Trends*, 1, 71–76.

2. Vinnik, M. A. (2010). On the role of astronomical education in teaching and development of students. *Bulletin of the Moscow State Regional University. Series: Pedagogy*, 2, 169–173.
3. Bezrukov, P. O. (2019). Opportunities for the use of digital technologies in astronomy lessons in upper secondary school to achieve educational outcomes. In *Teaching Physics and Astronomy in General and Vocational Education* (pp. 26–27).
4. Shefer, O. R., Lebedeva, T. N., & Nosova, L. S. (2017). Internet resources in teaching astronomy at school. In *Lomonosov Readings in Altai: Fundamental Problems of Science and Education* (pp. 850–853).
5. Khabarov, A. (2006). The use of Internet technologies in astronomy lessons. *Computer Tools in Education*, 2, 3–8.
6. Vyborova, N. N. (2019). The use of the Stellarium program in the study of astronomy at school and university. *Bulletin of Shadrinsk State Pedagogical University*, 3(43), 94–99.
7. Pavlivsky, Yu. G. (2021). A system of multi-level astronomy tasks as a means of forming subject competencies of students through the use of information and communication technologies. In *Shamov Pedagogical Readings of the Scientific School of Educational Systems Management* (pp. 201–203).
8. Stellarium. (n.d.). *Stellarium: Free open-source planetarium software*. <https://stellarium.org/>